

RTM PROCESS SIMULATION BY USING XFEM AND LEVELSET METHOD

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ABSTRACT

A numerical simulation program for Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) manufacturing process is developed using eXtended Finite Element Method (XFEM) combined with the level set method. The level set method is used to track the resin flow front at each time step. XFEM allows to obtaining better accuracy of the resin pressure field in the flow front region than the classical FEM. The enriched shape functions of XFEM are derived by using the level set values of the front region. Finally, the level set values are calculated by an implicit characteristic Galerkin method. The numerical fill time is compared with the analytical solution to validate this program.

Keywords: *Level set method, Process simulation, RTM process, XFEM*

1 Introduction

Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) process is widely used in the industries of transport. For the design of the manufacturing process, it is necessary to simulate the resin flow in the mold so as to avoid the formation of air voids which could cause critical defects in the product. One of the important points to track the resin flow in the mold is to provide accurate approximation at the moving resin flow front.

The fluid velocity field (pressure gradient field) is discontinuous at the fluid flow front in the mold. The eXtended Finite Element Method (XFEM) is well adapted to obtain more accurate solutions near the flow front by enriching the elements intersected by the flow front without any remeshing at each time step. XFEM has been often used to treat various discontinuity problems (crack or interface problems) and their results were satisfactorily validated [1-3].

The level set method has been used to track moving interfaces [4, 5]. The level set value at the interface location is set to zero, and the level set field is described by a signed distance function from the interface. For RTM process simulation, the level set

method has been recently used to track the resin flow front, because it predicts intuitively the flow front's position [6].

In this study, XFEM is implemented to obtain the resin pressure field. The enriched shape functions for the pressure field are defined by level set values following to Chessa et al. [1, 2]. One of the advantages to use XFEM is that the equilibrium system remains symmetric and positive definite. Moreover, the enrichment is only applied on the flow front region. Therefore, the number of additional DOF is not much increased.

The level set method is composed of two procedures. The first one is to transport the flow front, and the second is the reinitialization to keep the level set function close to the signed distance function. An implicit characteristic Galerkin FEM is used to stabilize numerical oscillations caused by the convective term in the governing equations [7, 8].

The present program is validated by a simple square plate. The mold fill time calculated by this program is compared with the analytical fill time.

2 Mathematical models

The present study is focused on tracking of the resin flow motion during RTM process. The resin flow is assumed as incompressible with isothermal conditions. The resin in the mold flows through the fiber preform. Because the fiber preform is considered as porous media, the resin velocity can be described by Darcy's equation:

$$\mathbf{u} = -\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu} \nabla p \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{u} is the fluid velocity, p the fluid pressure, \mathbf{K} the permeability tensor, and μ the fluid viscosity. The mass conservation of incompressible fluid is written by:

$$0 = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \quad (2)$$

Substituting Eq. (1) into Eq. (2), the governing equation in function of the fluid pressure yields:

$$\nabla \cdot \left(-\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu} \nabla p \right) = 0 \quad (3)$$

Boundary conditions are given as:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{in} &= p_0 & \text{at injection gates,} \\ p_{vent} &= 0 & \text{at vent gates,} \\ \frac{\partial p}{\partial n} &= 0 & \text{at mold wall.} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Transport equation of resin, derived from the mass conservation law for incompressible fluid, is written as:

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \phi = 0 \quad (5)$$

where ϕ is level set function. The position of flow front is described as the zero level set of a time-dependent function, in other words, the resin front motion can be matched with the zero level set position which is transported by the velocity \mathbf{u} .

The components of the permeability tensor K_{ij} are modeled by the Carman-Kozeny equation as:

$$K_{ij} = \frac{1}{k_{ij}} \frac{R_f^2 (1 - V_f)^3}{4 V_f^2} \quad (6)$$

where k_{ij} is Kozeny constant, R_f the fiber radius, and V_f the fiber volume fraction. The fluid viscosity μ in isothermal condition is time independent. We

assume that the air is also incompressible due to its low velocities. Therefore, the viscosity on the entire domain is defined as:

$$\mu = H(\phi)\mu_r + (1 - H(\phi))\mu_a \quad (7)$$

where μ_r is resin viscosity and μ_a is air viscosity. $H(\phi)$ is defined as:

$$H(\phi) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \phi < -h \\ \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\phi}{h}\right) & \text{if } |\phi| \leq h \\ 0 & \text{if } \phi > h \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where h is the mesh size.

3 Numerical methods

3-1 XFEM

The main advantage of XFEM in this study is to obtain accurately the pressure field without remeshing on the flow front region [1]. The computing domain is divided into two regions: normal or enriched one. The enriched region is composed of the elements having enriched nodes, which are added to the elements intersected by the flow front, as shown in Fig. 1. The normal region is composed of the elements without any enriched node.

Fig.1: Location of enriched nodes.

The standard finite element approximation is performed on the normal region. The pressure of the enriched region is approximated as:

$$p^h = \sum_{I \in N} N_I p_I + \sum_{J \in N_{enrich}} N_J^{enrich} a_J \quad (10)$$

where p^h is the approximate fluid pressure, N_I the normal shape functions, and p_I the nodal values. N_J^{enrich} and a_J are the enriched shape functions and the additional nodal parameters at the enriched node, respectively. The enriched shape function is defined by:

$$N_j^{enrich} = N_j(|\phi| - |\phi_j|) \quad (11)$$

where $|\phi|$ is the absolute level set function and $|\phi_j|$ is the absolute level set values at the enriched nodes. These enriched shape functions have two desirable properties. At first, they reflect the position of the flow front. Then, the value of each enriched shape function is equal to zero at its correspondent enriched node as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: $|\phi| - |\phi_j|$ for one-dimensional linear element.

The enrichment has two types; full or partial one. The full enrichment concerns the elements having only enriched nodes. The partial enrichment concerns the elements having both enriched and normal nodes. The partial enrichment is necessary to keep the pressure field continuous.

Fig. 3: Fully and partially enriched elements.

3-2 Level set method

The level set method is used to transport the resin. The level set value means signed distance from the flow front as shown Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Contours of level set values.

At the flow front, the level set value is equal to zero. The filled region with the fluid has a negative level set value, and the empty region has the positive.

The level set values are calculated through two procedures. The first one is to solve Eq. (5) for the transport of the flow front. After the first procedure, the nodes on the flow front have zero level set values. However, the level set values at the other region except the flow front are not the signed distance value. Therefore, a second procedure is employed in order to reinitialize the level set value to the signed distance. In other words, the second procedure modifies the level set value to satisfy the following condition:

$$\|\nabla \phi\| = 1 \quad (12)$$

We use the reinitialization method proposed by Peng et al. [5]:

$$\frac{\partial d}{\partial \tau} + \text{sign}(d_0)(\|\nabla d\| - 1) = 0 \quad (13)$$

where τ is the time variable for the reinitialization routine.

Here, the initial value d_0 is equal to the level set value and $\text{sign}(d_0)$ is the signature function which is -1 when ϕ is negative, zero when ϕ is zero, and +1 when ϕ is positive [5]. The solution of Eq. (13) replaces the level set value.

4 Numerical formulations

4-1 Pressure field

Using the standard Galerkin method, the weak form of Eq. (3) is written as:

$$\int_{\Omega} \left(\nabla \cdot \left(-\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu} \nabla p \right) \right) w dV = 0 \quad (14)$$

where w is a weight function and Ω is the full domain of the mold. And, the Green-Gauss theorem is applied to Eq. (14) to yield:

$$\begin{aligned} & - \int_{\Omega} \nabla w \cdot \left(-\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu} \nabla p \right) dV \\ & + \int_{\partial \Omega} w \left(-\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu} \nabla p \right) \cdot \mathbf{n} dV = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Boundary conditions are set as:

$$\left(-\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu} \nabla p \right) \cdot \mathbf{n} \Big|_{\text{wall}} = 0, p_{\text{vent}} = p_{\text{air}}, p_{\text{inject}} = p_{\text{inject}} \quad (16)$$

Approximation of the pressure field for the enriched region is performed by XFEM as described in the paragraph 3-1. The pressure approximation of normal region is given by:

$$p^h = \sum_{I \in N} N_I(x, y) p_I \quad (17)$$

4-2 Transport of the flow front

An implicit characteristic Galerkin FEM is used to stabilize numerical oscillations when of solving Eq. (5) [7, 8]. At first, Eq. (5) is discretized as:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi^{n+1} - \phi^n &= -\Delta t [\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \phi]_n \\ &+ \frac{\Delta t^2}{4} [\nabla \cdot ((\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) \cdot \nabla \phi)]_n \\ &+ \frac{\Delta t^2}{4} [\nabla \cdot ((\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) \cdot \nabla \phi)]_{n+1} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

By applying the standard Galerkin FEM procedure, the weak form of Eq. (18) is written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} (\phi^{n+1} - \phi^n) w dV &= -\Delta t \int_{\Omega} w \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \phi^n dV \\ &- \frac{\Delta t^2}{4} \int_{\Omega} \nabla w \cdot [(\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) \cdot \nabla \phi^n] dV \\ &- \frac{\Delta t^2}{4} \int_{\Omega} \nabla w \cdot [(\mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) \cdot \nabla \phi^{n+1}] dV \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

We use the same procedure for the reinitialization procedure. At first, Eq. (13) is modified as:

$$\frac{\partial d}{\partial \tau} + \mathbf{w} \cdot \nabla d = \text{sign}(d_0), \quad \mathbf{w} = \text{sign}(d_0) \frac{\nabla d}{\|\nabla d\|} \quad (20)$$

where $\text{sign}(d)$ is defined as:

$$\text{sign}(d) = \frac{d}{\sqrt{(\|\nabla d\| h)^2 + d^2}} \quad (21)$$

After applying the implicit characteristic Galerkin FEM, Eq. (20) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} (d^{n+1} - d^n) w dV &= \\ &- \Delta t \int_{\Omega} w (\mathbf{w} \cdot \nabla d^n - \text{sign}(d_0)) dV \\ &- \frac{\Delta t^2}{4} \int_{\Omega} \nabla w \cdot [(\mathbf{w} \otimes \mathbf{w}) \cdot \nabla d^n] dV \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

$$- \frac{\Delta t^2}{4} \int_{\Omega} \nabla w \cdot [(\mathbf{w} \otimes \mathbf{w}) \cdot \nabla d^{n+1}] dV$$

4-3 Computational procedures

Fig. 5 shows the whole computational scheme. The first step is to read input data, such as mesh information, material properties and boundary conditions, and to initialize the pressure field and level set values. After, the fluid velocity is calculated from the pressure field, and the level set values are calculated. The reinitialization of level set values is done if necessary. Then, the index of nodes is set such as the enriched nodes by 1 and the normal nodes by 0 to attribute the correspondent shape functions. The second and third steps are continued until the mold filling is completed. The parallel multi-frontal solver developed by Kim et al. [10] is used to solve the discretized equilibrium equations.

Fig. 5: Global computing scheme.

5 Validation

A simple square plate shown in Fig. 6 is treated to assess the present methods. The side length of the plate is 0.1 m and its thickness is 0.001 m. The preform is considered as isotropic porous media and its permeability is $5.123 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2$. The resin and the air viscosity are 0.2 and $1.5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$, respectively. Input pressure is 1 MPa at the injection gate and 0 at the vents. The element type is the three-node triangular element. The number of elements of irregular mesh is 8252 and the number of nodes is 4247.

At first, we validate the reinitialization procedure (Eq. (20)) to reset the level set values as Eq. (12). The flow front in the mold (Fig 6) is fixed at the radius of 0.025 from the injection gate. We put the level set values as:

$$\|\nabla \phi_0\| = 2 \quad (23)$$

The reinitialization routine of Eq. (22) is repeated until Eq. (12) is satisfied. As shown in Fig. 7, the level set values were well converged after 70 iterations.

Fig. 6: A square plate and its mesh with four vents at the corner and an injection gate at the center.

Fig. 7: Isovalue contours of level set values: (A) Upper view on x-y plan, (B) Side view in x axis.

To verify the transport of flow front, Eq. (19), the transport velocity is put to have a uniform expansion at each time step. We tested the transport of flow front from the position at 0.025 m to 0.03 m. As shown in Fig. 8, the isovalue contours of level set values are expanded uniformly as the imposed input conditions without numerical oscillation.

Fig. 8: Isovalue contours of the level set values: (A) Flow front at 0.025 m, (B) at 0.03 m.

Now, we put two injection gates at (0.05, 0.025) and (0.05, 0.075) in x and y coordinates to verify the merging of fronts. Two flow fronts are in contact at the beginning. After a few iterations, the two fronts are merged and the flow front position is changed as shown in Fig 9.

Fig. 9: Merging of two flow fronts: (A) Initial stage, (B) Merged stage.

Fig. 10 shows the pressure distribution of resin flow passing through the fiber preform in the mold during RTM process. The resin fill time of the mold obtained by the present methods is 1.32 sec. And the analytical solution suggested by Boccard et al. [11] gives 1.28 sec (Table 1). The difference between the two solutions is 3.2%.

Fig. 10: Pressure distribution in the mold at different times during RTM process.

$t_{fill} = M \left(\frac{r_{max}}{R_0} \right)^2 \left[2 \ln \left(\frac{r_{max}}{R_0} \right) + \left(\frac{R_0}{r_{max}} \right)^2 - 1 \right], \quad M = \frac{\mu(1-V_f)R_0^2}{4K_{iso}P_0}$	
Maximum moving distance (r_{max})	0.061m
Radius of the inlet port (R_0)	0.0015m
Fiber volume fraction (V_f)	0.44

Table 1: Analytical solution of the fill time t_{fill} for RTM process [11].

6 Conclusion

We developed a RTM process simulation program using XFEM combined with the level set method, so as to track more accurately the flow front during resin filling in the mold. The most important advantage of the present method is that the enriched shape functions are defined by the level set function and values so as to describe the pressure distribution according to the flow front's position.

The transport of resin flow, using the implicit characteristic Galerkin FEM, was validated through a simple square plate to stabilize numerical oscillations caused by the convective term in the governing equations. The resin flow of RTM process was also validated by comparing the fill time of the mold with the analytical solution on the same example. The difference between the obtained results and the analytical solutions was negligible.

The next step of this study is to minimize computing efforts in order to treat more complex structures such as industrial cases. Some industrial examples will be presented when of the oral presentation.

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